

A Method of Deoxygenation Reaction of Lead(IV) Acetate with α , β -Unsaturated Steroidal Ketoximes

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YUKAWA and coworkers¹ reported deoxygenation of a number of keto and aldoximes in acetic acid with lead(IV) acetate. To the best of our knowledge deoxygenation of α , β -unsaturated steroidal oximes with this reagent is not reported. The present note deals with the reaction of Pb(OAc)₄ with 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one oxime(I)² and its 3 β -chloro analogue(II)³.

	R	X
(I)	OAc	NOH
(II)	Cl	NOH
(III)	OAc	O
(IV)	Cl	O

The reaction of oximes(I) and (II) in dry benzene with Pb(OAc)₄ provided invariably 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one⁴(III) and 3 β -chloroketone⁵(IV) respectively in excellent yield, thus giving an easy method for purification of such compounds in multi-step synthesis of steroidal compounds.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer in Nujol. N.M.R. spectra were run in CdCl₂ with A60 Varian instrument with TMS as the internal standard. Ultraviolet spectra were determined in 95% ethanol with an Unicam Sp 800 spectrophotometer. (s, singlet; br, broad; W_{1/2}, half band width).

Reaction of 3 β -acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one oxime(I) with lead(IV) acetate :

The oxime(I) (2.0 g) dissolved in dry benzene (100 ml) was treated with lead tetra acetate (4.0 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 hrs. The solvent was removed under pressure and oil thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel (ca. 40 g). Elution with pet. ether-ether (15 : 5) provided

the ketone(III) which was crystallized from pet. ether (1.68 g), m.p. 161-163° (reported⁴ m.p. 164°).

U. V. : λ_{\max} 238 nm

I. R. : ν_{\max} 1730(CH₃-C=O), 1670 (-C=C-O), 1630 (-C=C-), 1240 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-).

N.M.R. : δ 5.6 s (C₆-H), 4.65 br (C₃- α H; W_{1/2} = 16 Hz; axial)⁶. 1.98 s (C₃ β -O-C-CH₃), 1.22 s (C₁₀-CH₃), 0.67 (C₁₃-CH₃), 0.83 and 0.89 (other methyl protons).

Reaction of 3 β -chlorocholest-5-en-7-one oxime(II) with lead(IV) acetate :

The oxime (II) under identical reaction conditions (same amounts of reactants were used) provided ketone (IV), (1.73 g), m.p. 144-145° (reported⁵ m.p. 144-145°).

U. V. : λ_{\max} 243 nm

I.R. : ν_{\max} 1675 (-C=C-C=O), 1635 (-C=C-), 768 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl).

N.M.R. : δ 5.38 s (C₆-H), 3.86 br (C₃- α -H; W_{1/2} = 20 Hz; axial), 1.25 s (C₁₀-CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₃-CH₃), 0.83 and 0.93 (other methyl protons).

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